

TEACHING PRIMARY STUDENTS TO THINK CREATIVELY IN THE LESSON PROCESS

Buvraev Akram Rustam o'g'li
Jizzakh State Pedagogical University
Part-time teacher

Annotation : This article discusses the problem of using interactive methods in primary education native language lessons, the extent to which they increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The author also discusses the features of using non-traditional methods in concentrating the student's attention, developing resourcefulness , and creativity .

Keywords : Pedagogical technology, interactive method, ability, style, resourcefulness, creativity, unconventional methods, creative thinking , critical method .

As is known, the main task of primary education is to provide students with in-depth knowledge using methods that teach independent thinking and develop creative thinking. To achieve this goal, new pedagogical technologies have been introduced into the educational process. New pedagogical technologies play an important role in the intellectual development and maturity of primary school students. One of the most popular types of pedagogical technologies today is interactive methods.

Interactive methods are a joint activity of the student and the teacher, which teaches students to think creatively, draw the necessary conclusions, analyze and apply the acquired knowledge in practice. The main task of the teacher is to give students a clear direction, to make the right conclusions. Interactive methods are also important in that the teacher never sharply rejects the student's opinion, but only makes the right conclusion, as a result of which the student realizes his mistake and does not stop thinking, and constant activity between them is ensured. In world pedagogical practice, the development of learning motivation is recognized as a factor in strengthening students' interest in learning, mastering the basics of science and stimulating independent cognitive activity. In particular, it is important to develop creative thinking in students based on an innovative and didactic system for developing creative thinking in students, a competency-based approach based on Life Skills.

In this article, we will talk about "Creativity", first of all, let's get acquainted with the introduction of this term into science. The word creativity was first used in 1922 by the American scientist D. Simpson. This term describes the ability of a person to abandon the stereotyped, stereotypical, habitual thinking. Creativity is a person's ability to come up with unusual ideas, thoughts, find unique, original solutions to problems, and abandon traditional forms of thinking. Rogers (1944) understands creativity as the identification of new solutions to problems and new ways of expressing something, an event, a situation. Creativity is a creative ability that characterizes an individual's readiness to generate new ideas and is part of giftedness as an independent factor. A person's creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, emotions, and certain types of activities.

It is known that young children have unstable attention, which can cause some problems for 1st graders. In this situation, interesting interactive methods are of great importance in concentrating students' attention. Performing visual tasks for students encourages them to think, be resourceful, and creative, and also develops their written and oral speech, increasing their vocabulary. The following methods give effective results in developing the resourcefulness of primary school students and the ability to remember letters: The "Sunflower" method. In the middle of the sunflower picture, vowels are written, and consonants are written around it. Students form several words by combining

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consonants and single vowels. During the game, the vowels in the middle can also be replaced. Students independently write the words they have made in their notebooks. All students participate equally in this process. The teacher encourages and evaluates those who participate most actively during the lesson. We can use this method both in writing lessons and in alphabet lessons. The more letters a student learns, the more words they can make by combining these letters. We can make such words from the letters given in the first and second sunflowers. For example: world, cherry, father, sky, master, brother, sleep. After completing the alphabet textbook, in the 1st grade native language book, students are first given information about "Sound and letter". The topics gradually become more complicated. This situation creates a certain difficulty and causes students to get bored with the lesson, albeit a little. In such cases, the use of interactive methods gives effective results. Our sunflower method shown above is a clear example of this.

The initial exercises of the "**Sound and Letter**" section are also given to form students' oral speech. This method can be used to strengthen the lesson. This method serves to organize native language lessons in an interesting way, prevent students from getting bored in lessons, and assess more students in a short time.

"Sinquain" method. The word "sinquain" means "five" and means "a poem of five lines that does not rhyme." Using the "Sinquain" method, students write a poem of five lines that do not rhyme. According to this, the first line can consist of one word and be a noun, the second line can consist of two words and be adjectives, the third line can consist of three words and be verbs, the fourth line can contain a complete proverb, and the fifth line can contain a word that is synonymous with the word in the first line. This method can be used by students in grades 2-3, after they have acquired an understanding of word classes. In the 2nd grade native language textbook, the vocabulary section provides initial morphological concepts about words that denote the name, action, sign, number and order of a person and thing. The teacher listens to the student's opinion and at the same time teaches the students to pay attention to each other's words. Objections or additions are also expressed through words such as "respectfully", "agreeing with your opinion", "we also had some opinions". In a lesson organized in this way, the student begins to think freely without any pressure and openly expresses his thoughts, learning to respect others.

In primary education, the mother tongue should serve to develop students' logical thinking, increase their vocabulary, develop oral and written speech (i.e., correct reading and writing), and create a basis for studying phonetics, lexis, word formation, and grammar. It is known that conducting dictionary work in the mother tongue lesson also arouses interest in students about the definition of unfamiliar words. It is advisable for the student to independently search for the definition of these words. In this case, the following method not only increases the students' vocabulary, but also teaches them to work with a dictionary.

The use of interactive methods in lessons should be organized in such a way that all students in the class are activated, that is, during the lesson a certain part of the educational material is studied independently by the students. The teacher is also the organizer, leader, and supervisor of the educational process. Students should feel free in the classroom and the educational activity should satisfy them emotionally, only then they can freely express their thoughts. Among the many factors determining the development of the creative abilities of a primary school student, in the process of mastering exercises in native language lessons, the child can also develop creative thinking, imagination, thinking, and communication skills. In this process, the child and the teacher together become a system of open problems that are subject to the child's specific creative thinking. This

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process should be carried out in forms that are convenient for the young student. Within the framework of this theory, the effective use of methods that develop creative thinking ensures the success of the lesson, which is determined by the creation of a pedagogical scenario by the teacher and the mastery of the indicative basis of new actions by young students in the process of creative activity.

The following are methods for developing creative thinking in conducting and organizing native language lessons in primary grades: The method of immersion. This involves the simultaneous perception of various types of exercises. This method contributes to the creation of a coherent literary text, a more complete assimilation of information, and evokes a vivid emotional and sensory response due to its deep penetration into the world of sound and words.

Contrast method . It is carried out in the form of contrasting tasks in various exercises. The contrast method allows you to contrast tasks, arouse interest in students, activate the manifestation of emotional responses. For each lesson, the teacher should choose such a range that will help to form interest in the world around them in young students.

In conclusion, the teacher must be well versed in such technology and be able to apply it correctly in practice, taking into account the characteristics of the language materials being studied. The more effective forms of teaching are used, the higher the level of interest of students in the subject of their native language.

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